

EFFECTIVENESS OF INTEGRATING INNOVATIVE AND DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING “SPECIAL METHODOLOGY OF MOTHER TONGUE INSTRUCTION” MODULE IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract. *The given article explores the improvement of the “Mother tongue teaching technology” module in training future surdopedagogues to develop the speech of deaf children. The study analyzes the effectiveness of implementing SMART technologies, organizing independent learning through interactive web tools, and using online assessment systems and media resources. It also provides methodological recommendations for integrating theoretical and practical components and fostering students’ reflective thinking. The results contribute to enhancing the efficiency and quality of professional training in surdopedagogy.*

Keywords: *surdopedagogy, deaf children’s speech, mother tongue, teaching technology, SMART approach, independent learning, integrative approach, innovative methods.*

INTRODUCTION

It is important to note that at present time Uzbekistan is entering a new stage and phase in every field. Higher education is a crucial link demonstrating the unparalleled impact of continuous education on national development, and a number of reforms are being carried out in this sector as well. The more prepared the graduates are for the labor market, the more the welfare of the people and the active participation of families in socio-economic relations are ensured. The Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, PD-2909, dated April 20, 2017, “On Measures for the further development of the Higher Education System”, and PD-3775, dated June 5, 2018, “On Additional measures to improve the quality of education in Higher Education Institutions and ensure their active participation in the ongoing comprehensive reforms in the country”, as well as the Presidential Decree PD-5847, dated October 8, 2019, “On Approving the concept for the development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030”, have specifically identified the task of advancing higher education to a new stage in terms of content, organizational-pedagogical structure, and international cooperation.

In particular, the integration of innovative, especially digital, technologies into the teaching of scientific modules in higher education has been chosen as a priority direction. The relevance of this task is connected with optimizing the continuous education system in the country according to international trends and standards, ensuring the quality and competitiveness of personnel training in higher education, and applying effective methods in the pedagogical process. The Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022, “On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026”, emphasizes pressing tasks such as promoting scientific research and innovation activities, creating effective mechanisms for their practical implementation, and establishing specialized scientific-experimental laboratories, high-tech centers, and technoparks within higher education institutions and research institutes. [1, p.21]

METHODS

Training of specialists in the field of special pedagogy is carried out in several higher education institutions in our country. In particular, personnel are trained at Uzbekistan National University of Pedagogy, as well as the state pedagogical institutes in Kokand, Chirchik, Jizzakh, Namangan, Fergana and Nukus. Special pedagogy has four independent branches: Oligophrenopedagogy, Surdopedagogy, Logopedics, and Typhlopedagogy. Currently, curricula and personnel training are being conducted in the directions of Oligophrenopedagogy, Surdopedagogy and Logopedics. The Typhlopedagogy direction has not yet implemented targeted admissions.

The Surdopedagogy direction focuses on training specialists in the education of deaf and hard-of-hearing children. This field has its own development history and methodological foundations. The Uzbekistan National University of Pedagogy serves as the primary institution for developing curricula, academic programs, and working plans in Surdopedagogy. It is well known that speech is an important social factor in the development of deaf and hard-of-hearing children. The earlier attention is given to speech development in these children, the more effectively they will be prepared to engage in every stage of continuous education. Their speech development occurs based on the principles of their native language. That is, for a child, the language that is their mother tongue should guide the development of their speech. [2, p.18]

Therefore, “Special methods for teaching the mother tongue” Module occupies a particularly important place in the training of specialists in this field. A specialist who has thoroughly mastered the methodology of teaching language to deaf and hard-of-hearing children is considered a key factor in ensuring the quality of the educational process in special education institutions and promoting the socialization of these children [3, p.58]. The necessity and structure of teaching the subject “Technology of mother tongue instruction” arises from the specific characteristics of the current period, which is undergoing fundamental and innovative changes. Currently, in connection with the scientific work plan of Kokand State University, experimental-research work is being conducted under the topic: “Methodology for preparing future surdopedagogues to develop the speech of deaf children.”

RESULTS

Within the research, initial analytical work concluded that it is necessary to integrate innovative technologies into the teaching of this module, particularly using computer technologies to organize students’ independent work and developing assignments accordingly. Therefore, we developed recommendations for using SMART technologies in setting objectives and creating methodological complexes for topics in the teaching of “Technology of mother tongue instruction”. Additionally, experimental-research work revealed several challenges in teaching courses at higher education institutions and organizing students’ independent work. For instance, in teaching the subject “Technology of mother tongue instruction,” topics are studied in the form of small texts or general scenes, which are not logically connected and are not systematized in blocks. Integrative approaches are crucial in teaching and learning the mother tongue. In the pedagogical process of higher education institutions, applying an integrative approach involves harmonizing the internal and external interrelated areas of a system or a complete section.

In training defectology specialists, the integrative approach is used to ensure the coherence of professional knowledge, skills, and competencies, as well as vocational-pedagogical techniques, verbal and non-verbal communication, and similar elements. We focused on increasing the effectiveness of independent learning in teaching the “Technology of mother tongue instruction”

module because, in the absence of monitoring independent learning outcomes, the following patterns are observed in students' behavior:

- insufficient competitiveness;
- low interest in creative and independent thinking;
- habit of mechanically copying ready-made information;
- completing assignments based on a formal approach rather than an analytical approach grounded in acquired skills and competencies;
- low personal responsibility for ensuring the quality and effectiveness of the learning process during independent study.

DISCUSSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The situations described above reduce the effectiveness of reinforcing theoretical lessons through independent learning assignments. Therefore, we recommend applying various projects and technologies during independent study and using a set of essential tools for teaching the subject. The necessary tools for teaching "Technology of mother tongue instruction" module are as follows:

Web Tools. There is a high demand for online electronic information and educational resources relevant to the subject. In practice, it was observed that teachers and students in the field of Special Pedagogy primarily use Russian internet sites and resources. In the future, a list of national resources for this field is being developed. Enriching web tools provides extensive opportunities for both practical exercises and independent knowledge acquisition. We propose structuring these tools as follows:

1. Working curriculum for the "Technology of Mother Tongue Instruction" module. This is aligned with the state educational standard for the 110000 – Pedagogy education field and the qualification requirements for the 60112700 – Special Pedagogy (Surdopedagogy) undergraduate program. It allows students to familiarize themselves with the requirements for their professional competency level. The module includes the syllabus, program, BCM (basic competency modules), competencies, and qualification requirements.

2. "Pedagogical Mastery" or "Specialist Platform" project, which presents various forms of mastering the module, including web lectures, seminars, master classes, practical sessions, trainings, animated videos, electronic albums, media files, audio and video materials, slides for electronic presentations, and web documents illustrating visual materials.

3. Media Corner. This includes materials that enable effective mastery of both theoretical and practical knowledge within the module. These materials include lecture texts or collections of theoretical materials, electronic presentations, e-textbooks, electronic study guides, electronic instructional-methodical manuals, and collections of exercises and problems.

4. Glossary. Special supplementary materials related to the module, including encyclopedias, reference books, dictionaries, and normative-methodical as well as normative-technical documents.

5. Current, Midterm, and Final Assessments. Collections of control questions, practical tasks, or test assignments corresponding to the topics specified in the curriculum or the entire study module.

6. "Future Specialist Platform." Students upload media resources prepared according to the subject content as independent learning assignments. This includes videos produced during professional practice, professional advertisements, and brochures.

7. Online Assessment- Interactive System. Assignments are given to students, with the opportunity for self-assessment. Importantly, the prepared tests and assignments must correspond to each specific topic.

CONCLUSION

The results of the study indicate that organizing the “Technology of mother tongue instruction” module based on modern pedagogical and information-communication technologies significantly improves the quality of education in training future surdopedagogues to develop the speech of deaf children. Within this module, the use of SMART technologies to set goals and outcomes, organizing students’ independent learning through interactive web tools, and effective use of online assessment systems and media resources positively influence the formation of professional competencies in future surdopedagogues.

During the research, several problems were identified in the implementation of the “Technology of mother tongue instruction” module: the educational content was not logically systematized, effective monitoring of independent learning activities was not established, and students’ creative thinking and reflective approaches were insufficiently developed. These issues highlighted the need to introduce an integrative approach in improving the module, ensure interdisciplinary connections, and use practice-oriented methodological tools. The recommendations and proposals developed as a result of the study suggest organizing the “Technology of mother tongue instruction” module in a digital learning environment enriched with SMART approaches, web tools, the “Future Specialist Platform,” the “Media Corner,” and online assessment systems. This organization aims to enhance the effectiveness of the educational process focused on developing the speech of deaf children. Thus, the results of the research are of significant theoretical and practical importance for developing the professional training of future surdopedagogues based on innovative and integrative methods and for improving scientific and practical mechanisms aimed at ensuring the speech development of deaf children.

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